

EXPLORING THE LANGUAGE AWARENESS OF STUDENTS: A MIXED METHOD INQUIRY

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Exploring the Language Awareness of Students: A Mixed Method Inquiry

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Abstract

The study aimed to explore the language awareness of English education students in a local college. This study engaged mixed method design, utilizing parallel convergent approach. The participants of the study were the English education students from all year levels. There were 214 students who were randomly selected for quantitative and 10 students for the qualitative phase: five for in-depth interview and five for focus group discussion who were purposively selected. Based on the results of the study, it was determined that the level of language awareness is high. Also, in the results of qualitative data, there were five essential themes that emerged from the lived experiences of students: gaining motivation for language learning and teaching, having the ability to uncover underlying meanings and messages in texts, utilizing English as a tool for effective communication, having different means of identifying proper approach in communication, and enhancing language proficiency and communication strategies. On the other hand, there were four essential themes which emerged from the insights of English education students which are: the importance of establishing engagement for effective language expression, the significance of foundational knowledge and communicative competence in learning a language, the interconnectedness of language learning and performances, and the value of employing variety of language materials and actual activities. Moreover, the results from the quantitative and qualitative converged when they were being corroborated.

Keywords: *language awareness, English education students, mixed methods, Philippines*

Introduction

Understanding the function of language in human thought, learning, and social interactions is known as language awareness. It involves understanding the complex connections between language and culture as well as the power and control that can be exerted via language (Van Lier, 1995, as cited in Hèlot et al., 2018). Language awareness was first introduced in the 1950s, and leading linguists and researchers such as Hawkins and Halliday backed the notion that teaching language should help students deal with language-related problems in general rather than just helping them master the target language (Mastas, 2001). In addition, despite the availability of materials to be used to improve one's language awareness, there are still students who lack language awareness such as linguistic issues like grammar and vocabulary, because they prioritize conveying and understanding the message over accuracy, leading to ineffective correction and internalization of language errors (Flora, 2021).

In Saudi Arabia, teaching English language was a challenge as students are less exposed to the language resulting to their low language awareness. Despite the efforts of the Ministry of Education, there are still problems in teaching and learning English. Since they begin learning English in the final year of elementary school, students are not exposed to enough of the language (Al-Nofaie, 2010). Accordingly, Saudi Arabian pupils begin studying English in middle school with the sole goal of passing the test. Their inadequate exposure to English language vocabulary, grammar, concept structure, spelling, and reference impacts their writing and speaking skills (Al-Khasawneh, 2010). Despite studying for almost 9 years, the learners still encounter various problems in their communication process, due to their lack of opportunity to practice English apart from the classroom. Furthermore, the study further established that language awareness is important because more exposure to the language allows students to practice and apply their knowledge of the language in real-life situations. Instruction and interaction through English alone may lead to deeper language awareness and better linguistic ability on the part of the students for resolving linguistic problems effectively (Ashraf, 2018).

On the other hand, in the Philippines, language awareness is one of the deciding features of everyday communication. Especially, that Philippine education utilizes the English language as a medium of instruction, which students often require to shift between languages predominantly used in the country like English and Filipino and are blatantly aware of their linguistic choices. To wit, this is obviously demonstrated through the use of terms meant to humorously underscore the difficulty of shifting between languages or understanding complex English language use, as in "nosebleed.". Such term reflects their difficulty in understanding English language, especially when complex terms or nuances are used during conversations. Moreover, language awareness not only pertains to knowing multiple languages but is also self-awareness of the social and cultural implications of language use in different contexts, in which many Filipino students find difficult to comprehend or utilize in their communication process (Osborne, 2018).

Furthermore, exploring the language awareness of students, particularly in the English language, holds significant importance in the society. English is widely recognized as a global language and plays a pivotal role in various domains, including education, business, and communication. Understanding students' language awareness towards English language can provide valuable insights into their proficiency levels, language learning experiences, and the impact of English language awareness in their experiences in the English education program. This research can help inform curriculum development, teaching methodologies, and policy-making decisions aimed at enhancing English language education in the Philippines, ultimately preparing students for global opportunities and promoting

linguistic competence in an increasingly interconnected world.

Moreover, despite the existing research on language awareness among students, there is a notable research gap regarding the specific focus on English language awareness of students in the context of Philippine English education programs. While some studies in the Philippines have explored language awareness of students, such as “Awareness of Philippine English: The Case of Undergraduate Students” by Ali (2022), the study mainly focused on the language awareness of undergraduates in regard to their awareness of the existence of the Philippine English as a variety of World Englishes. On the other hand, another study that explored the language awareness of Filipino under the Philippine education program is the study of Hernandez (2022) entitled “Philippine English and Teaching It: Awareness and Attitudes of Grassroots Filipino English Language Teachers,” in which the study mainly focused on the language awareness of the Filipino teachers toward the existence of Philippine English as a variety of World Englishes and their attitudes towards teaching it. Thus, there is a need for comprehensive research that delves into English education students' language awareness of the English language. Bridging this research gap can provide a nuanced understanding of the level of students' language awareness specifically towards English language, and contribute to the development of effective language education strategies and policies in the Philippine educational context.

The findings will be determined after the data gathered. This study aimed to investigate the language awareness of English major students. The audience of this study was the officially enrolled students of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology, a local college of Kapalong Davao del Norte. The target audience is the English major students of KCAST and the researcher utilized random sampling technique to determine the number of audiences.

Research Questions

In this study, a convergent parallel mixed method research was employed to broadly describe the language awareness of students in learning English. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of language awareness of English education students?
2. What are the experiences of English education students with regard to their language awareness?
3. What are the insights of English education students with regard to their language awareness?
4. To what extent does the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

A mixed method design was used in this study, which combines qualitative and quantitative elements to give a more thorough explanation of the research subject. Halcomb and Hickman (2015) asserted that this integration, which can take place at any point during the study process, is essential to the rigor of mixed methods research. In order to provide a more comprehensive explanation of the study problem, the qualitative and quantitative components are linked through a process known as "mixing".

Bryman (2007) asserts that mixed methods research is essential to studies that go beyond simple validation. It makes it possible to combine several research techniques, which results in a thorough and integrated viewpoint on the topic of investigation. This method enables a deeper comprehension of the topic being studied in addition to validating the research. Researchers may uncover new information by integrating the findings from several approaches that could have gone unnoticed with a single-method strategy.

For this study, a convergent parallel mixed method research design was chosen. This architecture gives equal attention to both forms of data, which are gathered simultaneously. First, the survey will be gathered, and then focus groups or individual interviews will take place. Each of the two data sets will undergo independent analysis before the findings are pooled and evaluated. This design is suitable for the study since its goal is to investigate the relationships, contradictions, divergence, or convergence between the two data sources (Hanson et al., 2005).

In the convergent parallel design, sometimes referred to as the convergent/triangulation design, both quantitative and qualitative studies are conducted concurrently throughout the same stage of the research process. Because both approaches are given equal weight in this design, they can both contribute significantly to solving the research topic. This approach preserves the studies' autonomy throughout the data collecting and analysis phases before integrating the findings for the overall interpretation (Petrosyan, 2018).

In order to obtain a thorough grasp of the subject, this study was carried out utilizing a mixed-method design called the convergent parallel design. The qualitative and quantitative components of the research process were reflected (Morse, 1991). Convergent parallel designs involve the simultaneous use of both quantitative and qualitative approaches in the same phase of the research process, with equal weight given to each method, independent analysis of the two components, and joint interpretation of the findings. By directly contrasting the quantitative statistical data with the qualitative findings, the researcher sought to triangulate the methodologies for validation and corroboration. Two datasets were acquired for the study, examined independently, and contrasted (Demir & Pismek, 2018).

Consequently, this study used a descriptive-comparative methodology, which entailed contrasting and comparing the data gathered in

order to derive significant findings. This study is to ascertain the degree of language awareness of teacher education students and lay the groundwork for efficient teaching methods and tactics by employing both quantitative and qualitative research methods. Accordingly, both quantitative and qualitative research methodologies are used in the study (Richardson, 2018).

Furthermore, this study employed phenomenological inquiry to enhance the qualitative framework. Through the participants' experiences, this methodology helped them find and comprehend the rich surroundings. The focus of a phenomenology is on the similarities among a group's lived experiences. A group of people who have first-hand knowledge of a situation, event, or experience are usually interviewed. Documents and observations are examples of additional data types that can be employed (Creswell, 2013).

On the other hand, the phenomenological technique used in this study's qualitative phase reflects an epistemological perspective that recognizes the validity of many subjective truths. In order to establish themes based on the researcher's data, saturate the data from in-depth interviews, and gain insights into the community's social norms, qualitative data collection techniques like focus groups and one-on-one interviews were also used (Groenewald, 2004).

Participants

Quantitative Phase

The respondents of this study were the English education students from all year levels in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology during the second semester of S.Y. 2023-2024. They were chosen as the respondents because the study is about Language awareness of English education students in a local college. Since the study purports to involve students who are in the English education program in a local college, it was fitting and valid to include English education students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology.

Further, the respondents was determined through sampling, specifically, stratified random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This method involves dividing population into smaller groups, or "strata," and randomly selecting a sample from each stratum. The per-stratum samples were then combined to create an overall stratified random sample. An alternative to simple random sampling, stratified random sampling will ensure that each stratum is represented in the sample and can provide more accurate results when analyzing subgroups within the population (Nguyen et al., 2020).

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondent*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First Year	223	104	22.85%
Second Year	136	64	13.94%
Third Year	69	32	7.07%
Fourth Year	29	14	2.97%
Total	457	214	46.83%

This sampling method is particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents, which are the English education students were randomly selected based on strata, which in this case are all the year levels of the English education program in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. This also ensures that all of the respondents in the population had equal chances of being selected. The researcher wrote a formal request letter to the College Registrar and gained access to the population of English education students from all year levels. The researcher then gathered the data from the population of English education students to compute the sample. After getting the data, the researcher sent the information to her statistician for computation of the study sample.

The study was conducted among students enrolled in the English education program from all year levels. The institution has a total of 457 English education students, consisting of 223 first year students, 136 second year students, 69 third year students, and 29 fourth year students. However, the sample appropriate for the study was computed by the statistician, which includes 104 out of 223 first year students, 64 out of 136 second year students, 32 out of 69 third year students, and 14 out of 29 fourth year students. In total, 214 students were sampled out of 457 students in English education program.

Qualitative Phase

Table 1.2. *Profile of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-level</i>
IDI-01	Female	3rd year
IDI-02	Female	4th year
IDI-03	Female	1st year
IDI-04	Male	2nd year
IDI-05	Female	3rd year
FGD-01	Female	2nd year
FGD-02	Female	2nd year
FGD-03	Female	1st year
FGD-04	Female	3rd year
FGD-05	Female	3rd year

In contrast, qualitative research purposefully chose its subjects. Purposive sampling, a type of non-probability sampling, was used in this phase. Participants were chosen based on their ability to contribute to the research questions and improve comprehension of the phenomenon being studied (Kuper et al., 2008). Only 10 participants of English education students enjoined in the qualitative phase: five (5) for in-depth interview and another five (5) for focus group discussion. All of them were an English education student at KCAST and he or she is a 1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year or 4th year student. It was noted that participants in qualitative phase have not participated in the data collection of quantitative phase.

Instrument

Quantitative Phase

The researcher utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire for language awareness. The said questionnaire used a Five-point Likert Scale which had the following indicators: affective domain, social domain, power domain, cognitive domain, and performance domain. In a Five-point Likert Scale, participants were only required to rate and pick one box among one (lowest) to five (highest) in each question. Moreover, Likert Scale is good for measuring constructs, attitudes and stimuli which are not readily perceivable by human senses. After the formulation, the instrument had undergone validation from the panel experts.

Qualitative Phase

As to the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions was devised by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was used as a compass for the in-depth interviews. The participants were randomly selected who did not answer the survey questionnaire during the conduct of the quantitative phase, five were purposively selected to undergo the IDI and another five for the FGD. Interviews are suitable in gleaning insights, stories, experiences, opinions and other useful information which could not be expressed with the use of numbers.

Procedure

There are several steps in the data collection process. The following procedures will be followed during the conduct of the study:

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, a researcher-made questionnaire was used for the language awareness of the students. It was administered to a group of English education students in a face-to-face set-up. In addition, the researcher wrote a letter of request to the school administrator, asking for an approval to conduct the study to their respective school and students. The results were tallied, computed and analyzed to corroborate with the results of the qualitative data. The qualitative and quantitative phases of the study was made simultaneously.

Qualitative Phase

For the qualitative phase, a one-on-one interview was conducted to the identified participants in order to gather the lived experiences of the English education students with regard to their language awareness. An interview guide was used both for the in-depth interview and focus group discussion. Hence, to ensure authenticity of selection, the researcher invited the informants through personal contact and they were informed of the tasks to be and that includes the time set for everyone's convenience (Creswell, 2013).

The focus group discussion centered on the exploration of individuals' opinions, experiences, concerns, and desires regarding the specific issues at hand. According to Traynor's (2015), this method typically involves bringing together a group of individuals who share a common characteristic, facilitated by a researcher, to engage in group interactions, exchange perspectives on a specific topic, discuss personal experiences, and provide suggestions. It's important to note that the methodology of focus group research explicitly emphasizes the use of interaction. The discussions took various forms, including one-on-one sessions, and was recorded through voice recording, with additional notes taken.

Furthermore, in-depth or one-on-one interviews were also conducted to provide a valuable opportunity for exploring the perceptions of English education students regarding their language awareness. Ten (10) students was purposively selected for these interviews, which was conducted by the researcher. The in-depth interviews was voice recorded.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

In the quantitative data analysis, descriptive statistics such as the mean was utilized to assess the average responses of the respondents. The survey data, which was collected, serves as the basis for in-depth analysis. Upon retrieval of the questionnaires, the data was tallied and treated accordingly. The survey data was further analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for both descriptive and inferential statistics. These statistical treatments was applied to ascertain the status of English education students.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Regarding the qualitative data analysis, the researcher employed coding and thematic analysis. This involved examining the patterns

and themes that emerged from the utterances or statements of the participants/informants during the one-on-one and focus group interviews. The themes were formulated with the purpose of analyzing the lived experiences and insights of English education students in regards to their language awareness. The data was carefully analyzed to identify and extract relevant themes that sheds light on the research objectives and provide insights into the participants' experiences in this context.

Ethical Considerations

In order to uphold the trust of the English education students from KCAST, the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. Measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations are carefully addressed, aiming to maintain the trust of the participants throughout the course of the study.

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical principles including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality to ensure that ethical standards will be met. These principles guided the conduct of the study in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that underscores the importance of treating research participants with courtesy and respect, and acknowledging their autonomy in decision-making regarding their participation in a study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle necessitates providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they have a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent is a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signifies voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted ethically and in a manner that honors the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher obtained permission from the participants and arrange the schedule in advance to avoid conflicts with their classes or other obligations. This was made to ensure that the researcher's presence would not disrupt the participants' schedules and to avoid the need for rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

On the conduct of the study, the researcher established a respectful and courteous relationship with the participants and obtained their permission before recording the conversations. The researcher also allowed the participants to ask questions at any time and maintained the confidentiality of the in-depth interviews and focused group discussion. In addition, the participants had the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. By establishing rapport and acting with courtesy towards the participants, the researcher was able to conduct the study in an ethical and respectful manner.

Consent is a fundamental aspect of research ethics and serves as a way to show respect to research participants. By obtaining informed consent, the participants were made fully aware of the objectives and purpose of the research they were asked to participate in. Written consent was obtained from the participants, certifying their approval to take part in the in-depth interviews and focused group discussions. They were provided with information about the results and findings of the study, ensuring transparency and keeping them informed (Creswell, 2012).

To ensure the ethical conduct of the study, the researcher provided the participants with letters of permission and consent that outlines the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and make informed decisions about whether to participate. Participants who decided not to participate were allowed to leave without any explanations and were assured that their data would remain confidential. The researcher also informed the participants that they have the rights to be informed of the result of the study. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher was able to ensure that the study is conducted in a responsible and respectful manner.

Beneficence, as an ethical principle, emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees were maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

To adhere to the principle of beneficence, the researcher took steps to protect the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants' responses and personal identities. By taking these measures, the researcher was able to ensure the well-being and interests of the participants and demonstrate a commitment to ethical research practices.

Furthermore, the data which was collected from this research study were used only for the purposes outlined in the study. However, the results of the study may also be shared or disseminated through channels such as presentation to the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, or presentation at conferences, either locally, nationally, or internationally. By disseminating the results of the study, the researcher aims to share the findings and contribute to the broader knowledge base in their field of study.

Confidentiality towards the data, results and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques were used. Meaning, all personal identities of the participants were hidden and not shown. All materials including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data and others were eliminated right after the data is analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect the participants' identity and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher used discrete coding to denote each participant's responses. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the

participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, the researcher was able to protect the participants' identity and ensure that their privacy is respected.

Justice in the conduct of this study was upheld by ensuring that the rights of the participants who identified themselves as English education students were respected. Given that the study aimed to explore the language awareness of English education students, no rights of minor students were violated. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. English education students were not coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they so choose. In recognition of their contribution, tokens were provided to the participants, and they were duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Additionally, justice was ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013).

Results and Discussion

The investigation's quantitative and qualitative were presented in this chapter. The presentation of quantitative results started with the quantitative descriptive results which presents the level of language awareness of English education students. Consequently, the presentation of the results of the qualitative phase followed which includes the thematic analysis of the lived experiences and insights of English education students with regard to their language awareness.

Level of Language Awareness of English Education Students

Table 2. *Level of Language Awareness of English Education Students*

<i>Variables and Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>A. Affective Domain</i>		
1. learn English language better when I find it valuable to my studies.	4.33	Very High
2. eagerly learn the English language when I am motivated.	4.39	Very High
3. explore the forms and functions of English language when I am curious about it.	4.21	High
4. find learning the English language easier if I can relate it to real life situations.	4.23	High
5. find English language useful and important for communication inside and outside the school.	4.33	Very High
Category Mean	4.30	Very High
<i>B. Social Domain</i>		
1. can determine what form of language to use in different contexts or settings.	3.93	High
2. can communicate well with people with different cultures and behaviors.	3.80	High
3. can adapt to how the language is used in the society.	3.96	High
4. know what manner of speaking to be used when having conversation with different people.	4.09	High
5. manage to have a meaningful and enjoyable conversation with other people.	4.07	High
Category Mean	3.97	High
<i>C. Power Domain</i>		
1. can understand the meaning of spoken or written language used by others.	3.92	High
2. understand what is being said to me even in a figurative sense.	3.75	High
3. can identify hidden meanings within texts I read or hear.	3.76	High
4. can make assumptions of what is being told to me after I hear or read it.	3.82	High
5. know that language meanings and usage are influenced by societal norms.	3.87	High
Category Mean	3.82	High
<i>D. Cognitive Domain</i>		
1. consider proper words to use in a situation or conversation.	4.21	High
2. recognize my mistakes in grammar, form and structure while having a conversation.	4.08	High
3. can correct my mistakes in grammar, form and structure while writing or talking.	3.94	High
4. learn new words from my peers or instructors.	4.23	High
5. can recognize the different parts of speech in English.	3.97	High
Category Mean	4.09	High
<i>E. Performance Domain</i>		
1. can communicate well with others using the English language.	3.88	High
2. can speak what I intend to say using the English language.	3.83	High
3. can deliver information effectively in class reporting using the English language.	3.78	High
4. can share my thoughts and ideas during class discussion using English language.	3.82	High
5. can convey my message clearly to people I am having conversation with using the English language.	3.82	High
Category Mean	3.83	High
Overall Mean	4.00	High

Table 2 presents the level of language awareness of English education students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. It obtains a total mean score of 4.00 with a description of high. This means that the English education students show positive level of language awareness. Among the five indicators namely; affective domain, social domain, power domain, cognitive domain, and performance domain, the highest mean of 4.30 was obtained by the indicator affective domain described as very high

which can be interpreted that English education students shows extremely positive level of language awareness in terms of affective domain. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.82 was obtained by power domain described as high which can be interpreted that students show positive level of language awareness in terms of power domain. This implies that English education students place a high value on emotional responses, attitudes, and beliefs towards language learning and use as part of their language awareness of the English language.

Affective Domain. In terms of affective domain, the category mean is 4.30, which is described as very high. This shows that students manifest an extremely positive level of language awareness in terms of affective domain. Among the items under this indicator, eagerly learn the English language when I am motivated got the highest mean of 4.39 which is described as very high. On the other hand, the lowest under this indicator, eagerly learn the English language when I am motivated got the highest mean of 4.39 which is described as very high. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was the item, explore the forms and functions of English language when I am curious about it, with a mean of 4.21 which is described as high.

Social Domain. In terms of social domain, the category mean is 3.97, which is described as high. This shows that students manifest a positive level of language awareness in terms of social domain. Among the items under this indicator, know what manner of speaking to be used when having conversation with different people got the highest mean of 4.09 which is described as high. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was the item, can communicate well with people with different cultures and behaviors, with a mean of 3.80 which is described as high.

Power Domain. In terms of power domain, the category mean is 3.82, which is described as high. This shows that students manifest a positive level of language awareness in terms of power domain. Among the items under this indicator, can understand the meaning of spoken or written language used by others got the highest mean of 3.92 which is described as high. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was the item, understand what is being said to me even in a figurative sense, with a mean of 3.75 which is described as high.

Cognitive Domain. In terms of cognitive domain, the category mean is 4.09, which is described as high. This shows that students manifest a positive level of language awareness in terms of cognitive domain. Among the items under this indicator, learn new words from my peers or instructors got the highest mean of 4.23 which is described as high. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was the item, can correct my mistakes in grammar, form and structure while writing or talking, with a mean of 3.94 which is described as high.

Performance Domain. In terms of performance domain, the category mean is 3.83, which is described as high. This shows that students manifest a positive level of language awareness in terms of performance domain. Among the items under this indicator, can communicate well with others using the English language got the highest mean of 3.88 which is described as high. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was the item, can deliver information effectively in class reporting using the English language, a mean of 3.78 which is described as high.

Pseudonym of Participants

Shown in Table 3 is the pseudonym of participants. It can be gleaned in the table that the codes being used and the pseudonym in the focus group discussion and in-depth interview are being provided. The five participants in in-depth interview were coded and given a pseudonym. The first participant was Coded as IDI 001 with the pseudonym of Ms. Confident because during the interview, she was answering the questions with confidence. The second participant coded as IDI 002 with the pseudonym, Ms. Professional, because when she was answering the questions, the tone of her voice seemed very professional. The third participant coded as IDI 003 with the pseudonym Ms. Cutie, because she looked really cute in person. The fourth participant coded as IDI-04 with the pseudonym Mr. Shy, because he wanted to have our interview online as he seemed shy to have it in person. The last participant for in-depth interview coded as IDI-05 with the pseudonym Ms. Unready, it is because we always pause the recordings during the interview as she always says that she is not ready even I oriented her prior to the time of interview.

Table 3. Pseudonym of Participants

<i>Code</i>	<i>Pseudonym</i>
IDI-01	Ms. Confident
IDI-02	Ms. Professional
IDI-03	Ms. Cutie
IDI-04	Mr. Shy
IDI-05	Ms. Unready
FGD-01	Ms. Honest
FGD-02	Ms. Nervous
FGD-03	Ms. Expressive
FGD-04	Ms. Cautious
FGD-05	Ms. Patient

The five participants in focus group discussion were coded and given a pseudonym. The first participant coded as FGD-01 with the pseudonym, Ms. Honest, because during the interview she was very true with her answers and it reflected on her actions. The second

participant coded as FGD-02 with the pseudonym Ms. Nervous, while the interview was on going, she asked to pause for a while in order for her to calm herself. The third participant coded as FGD-03 with the pseudonym Ms. Expressive, because during the interview I observed that she always says what she feels and what is on her mind. The fourth participant coded as FGD-04 with the pseudonym Ms. Cautious, because she was careful with her answers, and she takes her time in answering the questions. Lastly, the fifth participant in focus group discussion coded as FGD-05 with the pseudonym Ms. Patient, because she is always the last participant to answer the questions, she patiently waits, and she answers when it is already her turn to do so.

The Lived Experiences of English Education Students with Regard to their Language Awareness

There are six essential themes which are created based on the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion on the first research question. They are; gaining motivation for language learning and teaching, having the ability to uncover underlying meanings and messages in texts, utilizing English as a tool for effective communication, having different means of identifying proper approach in communication, and enhancing language proficiency and communication strategies. The essential themes which emerged from the transcriptions of the participants' responses for the research question number one consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Gaining Motivation for Language Learning and Teaching. In the context of language learning and teaching, some experiences of students with regard to their awareness of the English language are the following: preparation towards teaching profession, and application in real-world context. It was mentioned by the participants that their awareness of the English language has shaped their perspectives of language learning and teaching, thus becoming a factor that motivates them in language learning and teaching. Specifically, some participants stated that their awareness of the English language enabled them to see the benefits of language learning as it serves as an important knowledge for their future career or profession. On the other hand, some stated that they were able to appreciate language learning and teaching as the learners saw its usefulness in real world contexts or applications.

Table 4.1. *Lived Experiences of English Education Students with Regard to Their Language Awareness*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Experiences in shaping language learning and teaching	Acquiring knowledge for their field of career Driving force for the learners to teach the language Appreciating the real-world application of English language Knowing how to utilize English language in the learning process	Preparation towards Teaching Profession Application in Real-world Context	Gaining Motivation for Language Learning and Teaching	Self-Determination Theory
English proficiency in text interpretation	Widens the vocabulary in English language Improved language comprehension Awareness of surface level understanding and deeper understanding to texts Critical analysis of literary pieces or texts Interpretation of messages or meanings in texts	Skills Developed in English Language Making Interpretation of Text Meaning	Having the Ability to Uncover Underlying Meanings and Messages in Texts	Interactive Reading Theory
Influence of language in interaction and foundation of relationships	English as a common language in communicating with foreigners or individuals who speak different language English language as a means of communication in different formal contexts Language use in social media platforms	Various Means of Communication	Utilizing English as a Tool for Effective Communication	Sociolinguistic Theory
Impact of language registers in choice of words	Identifying appropriate words or taboo words while talking to different individuals Utilizing word choice based on the background of the person and situation Knowing the level of formality to be used in different communicative situations Determines the manner of speaking one must employ in conversing with different individuals	Using Word Choice in Different Contexts Formality of Speaking	Having Different Means of Identifying Proper Approach in Communication	Communication Accommodation Theory
Effect of Language awareness in the effectiveness in communication using	Mental repository of language rules, grammar, and vocabulary Awareness of proper pronunciation of words	Linguistic Knowledge	Enhancing Language Proficiency and Communication	Theory of Communicative Competence

the English language	Ability to solve communication problems which may arise during communication process Avoid misunderstanding between the speaker and receiver of the information or message Knowing how to utilize the language in a way that will express the message of the speaker while addressing diverse backgrounds of the listener or the situation itself.	Strategic Competence in Language Use	Strategies
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Consequently, Ms. Cutie stated that language awareness was a motivator for her to teach the language in the future. Thus, contributing to her perspective of its purpose in her future teaching career. She affirmed that:

“On the other hand, in terms of teaching, I find language awareness as a motivator for me to want to share my knowledge of the language to others.” (IDI-03)

Similarly, Mr. Shy found language awareness important as he was able to appreciate his learning process. This is because he was able to see the application of the language to his future career. He affirmed that:

“By having awareness of the English language, I was able to appreciate learning and teaching of the said language, especially that I am able to recognize its importance to me and to my future career.” (IDI-04)

On the other hand, Ms. Confident emphasized that her language awareness enables her to see the importance of equipping the English education students with the knowledge that they can utilize even outside the classroom. She affirmed that:

“It has broadened my understanding that in the process of teaching and learning in English education, not only grammar and vocabulary are given emphasized, but also practical communication skills and real-world applications of English.” (IDI-01)

Likewise, Ms. Professional recognizes the role of language awareness in the utilization of the language. Thus, this affected her competence in language use. She affirmed that:

“Additional for that is it enables us to improve our active process in using our language acquisition, which improves or enables us or we, as a student, to really have that skill in using the English language. And of course, to help build competence, or being competent enough in using the English language.” (IDI-02)

Additionally, Ms. Nervous recognize that language awareness enabled her to understand the importance of English language in real-life application. Also, she stated that simply memorizing the grammar rules is not enough, since the importance lies on the usage of the language. She affirmed that:

“...helps me to understand that effective language learning and teaching that it should or must focus on practical usage or through communication skills rather than just knowing and memorizing rules.” (FGD-02)

Lastly, Ms. Cautious found language awareness valuable as it facilitated her participation in class. Through her language awareness, she was able to effectively communicate inside the classroom, contributing to her classroom engagement. She affirmed that:

“...I am able to communicate using the English language not just in the different situation, particularly in a classroom setting, during reporting, I am able to communicate with my classmates and deliver my idea into English language and become effective and have an effective communication” (FGD-04)

Having the Ability to Uncover Underlying Meanings and Messages in Texts. Another essential theme drawn from the responses of the participants is the having the ability to uncover underlying meanings and messages in texts with the following codes; vocabulary knowledge in English language, and interpretation of meaning. It was mentioned by the participants that their awareness of the English language allowed them to comprehend a wide range of vocabulary as well as be able to uncover deeper meanings within texts.

Consequently, Ms. Confident stated that her language awareness enabled her to comprehend texts more effectively. This is because she was able to improve her language skills in terms of word comprehension, which contributes to her overall comprehension. She affirmed that:

“And, when I encounter difficult texts or maybe passages, I approach them by considering the overall message rather than focusing on individual words. So, this um approach allows me to interpret the underlying meanings and comprehend the texts more thoroughly.” (IDI-01)

Also, Ms. Professional emphasized the importance of her language awareness in comprehending texts. Through her awareness, she was able to develop her comprehension which enabled her to interpret texts. She affirmed that:

“So, it enables me to understand, and also improve my comprehension, which enables me to interpret, let’s say, the symbols, the themes that, or the hidden meanings of that work or works.” (IDI-02)

Further, Ms. Nervous stated that her language awareness enabled her to recognize the need for her to improve her language skill. Thus, contributing to her overall comprehension. She affirmed that:

“My proficiency in English helps me to understand hidden meanings in text and if there are words or phrases that is new to me, I always find ways like searching online sources to widen my vocabulary and in that way, I can enlighten myself and know more about language.” (FGD-02)

Additionally, Ms. Cautious recognized the importance of language awareness in her capability to uncover meanings, since she was able to widen her knowledge of the language. Through her language awareness, she was able to learn the social functions of the language, as well as improve her language comprehension. She affirmed that:

“Proficiency in English influence my ability to uncover hidden meanings in text that I encounter, usually in story, reading a novel or poem that is related with our subject or topic, that I be able to understand, comprehend the different word written there and able to not just rely myself on AI or dictionaries and of course it widens my vocabulary and also use that words in different context.” (FGD-04)

On the other hand, Ms. Cutie emphasized the importance of language awareness in the ability of a person to recognize figurative language. This also results to her improved comprehension of the text. She affirmed that:

“My proficiency helped me become aware of deeper meanings in a text, like if whether there are figurative language or like if there is a deeper message behind a certain sentence.” (IDI-03)

Likewise, Mr. Shy he also emphasized that language awareness does not only improve language comprehension, but as well as recognizing deeper meanings of texts. Thus, allowing him to recognize the surface level of meaning and deeper meaning of texts. He affirmed that:

“Through my proficiency in English, I learned to not only comprehend texts based on its surface meaning, but I also recognize that it may have deeper meanings behind it. I also know how to analyze texts which contains complex ideas behind its sentence level of meaning.” (IDI-04)

Lastly, Ms. Honest stated that her proficiency of the language enabled her to uncover hidden meanings of texts. Thus, allowing her to understand the overall piece. She affirmed that:

“Through my proficiency, through my proficiency of the language I am able to uncover hidden meanings that will help me to understand the word or a text.” (FGD-01)

Utilizing English as a Tool for Effective Communication. This is the third essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants with the code; various means of communication. Participants confirmed that they were able to utilize English in various contexts as well as utilizing proper word choice due to their language awareness of the said language.

Consequently, Ms. Confident recognizes the significant impact of utilizing the English language, as it enabled her to communicate in different contexts. Through being aware of the usage of the English language, she was able to confidently impart her message to different individuals. She affirmed that:

“...English language significantly impacted my social interactions or relationships is during conversations with my teachers. As a student, I must be mindful of the English usage, especially considering the knowledge gap between myself and my instructors. Through this experience, I’ve learned to express myself confidently when communicating with my teachers and how to properly communicate to address my questions, which has greatly improved my social interactions with the use of English language.” (IDI-01)

Also, Ms. Cutie emphasized the role of the English language in communicating with different individuals. She stated that through her utilization of the English language, it became a away for her to interact effectively in the context of online games. She affirmed that:

“A specific scenario, is when I’m playing with my friends in online games, I really need to be able to use English language to communicate with them effectively since if they won’t be able to understand me then there might be misunderstanding, or our strategy will be disorganized.” (IDI-03)

Likewise, Ms. Unready also stated its importance in communicating with foreign individuals. This is because, it served as a common language to them. She affirmed that:

“One specific scenario where English language influenced my social interaction is when I got to talk with a foreigner, my friend's dad.” (IDI-05)

Similarly, Ms. Nervous emphasizes the role of English language in facilitating conversation between individuals who speak different languages. Through her awareness of the function of English, she was able to utilize the language for an effective communication process. She affirmed that:

“...meeting someone with different cultural backgrounds, so on that scenario English will serve as your medium or common language that you can use to communicate and understand that person, and also its culture and tradition despite the difference specially in the languages use.” (FGD-02)

Additionally, Ms. Expressive also stated her experience while interacting with a foreigner. She stated that through the use of English, she was able to have an effective communication with the foreigner. She affirmed that:

“A scenario where English language significantly influenced my social interactions or relationships when my aunt and her foreign husband visited us, and in order for us to understand each other I used to speak English language to communicate him.” (FGD-03)

Lastly, Ms. Cautious highlighted the use of English language in social media platforms. This is due to the reason that English language is the international language, utilized in order to communicate with foreigners, and having certain awareness of the rules and functions of the language will enable the speakers to utilize it effectively. She affirmed that:

“Specific scenario where the English language significantly influence my social interactions or relationships is having a communication with use of cellphone or social media communication between my relatives living in other country, and of course applying job where you are inter being interviewed with your background and background and experience.” (FGD-04)

Having Different Means of Identifying Proper Approach in Communication. Another essential theme drawn from the responses of the participants is the having different means of identifying proper approach in communication with the following codes; using word choice in different contexts and formality of speaking.

Consequently, Mr. Shy recognize the importance of his language awareness, in utilizing the English language appropriately based on the context. Through this, he was able to choose appropriate vocabulary in his conversation process. He affirmed that:

“Through my understanding of language registers, I became able to know what manner of speaking I would use, and what words I would avoid in a conversation with different individuals.” (IDI-04)

Similarly, Ms. Unready also recognized the important role of recognizing appropriate language to use in different contexts due to her language awareness. She affirmed that:

“I am considering the context or the situation before talking or choosing the words I use to communicate with different individuals.” (IDI-05)

Likewise, Ms. Nervous also recognized the importance of knowing the right words to use based on the context she is in. Through being aware of this, she was able to avoid misunderstandings in conveying her thoughts. She affirmed that:

“Understanding different language styles has a lot of benefits and it gives us the knowledge on how to use right words when talking to different people in order to avoid misunderstanding or misconceptions.” (FGD-02)

Additionally, Ms. Expressive recognizes the importance of being aware of different language registers. Through this awareness, she was able to choose appropriate words in communicating with people. She affirmed that:

“Language registers help me choose the right and appropriate words to use so that I won’t hurt someone's feelings, and language registers also allow me to choose words correctly that depends to the situation I am in.” (FGD-03)

Furthermore, Ms. Cautious also acknowledges that language awareness enables her to choose correct words that fits her idea. Thus, allowing her to avoid being misinterpreted. She affirmed that:

“...during communication with the use of English language I could be able to choose the right words that fits my idea or what I am going to say, in order to avoid misinterpretation or misconception.” (FGD-04)

On the other hand, Ms. Confident emphasizes that her awareness of language registers enabled her to determine the level of formality she should employ when talking with different individuals. Thus, contributing to her overall communication process. She affirmed that:

“Actually, my understanding of language registers makes me aware that various situations demand or require different levels of formality.” (IDI-01)

Similarly, Ms. Professional also emphasized the role of language register awareness in having a successful conversation. This is because, her awareness enables her to choose appropriate formality to employ while conversing with different individuals. Thus, allowing her to keep in mind the context she is in, and the language appropriate to utilize. She affirmed that:

“...it allows me to tailor my language to suit a specific context and the audience. Because we cannot simply use words that are very out of context, or the person who we are talking to. So, whether you are communicating formally or let’s say casual with friends, really you have to adjust your vocabulary...” (IDI-02)

Lastly, Ms. Nervous also recognize the importance of being aware to language registers. She stated that through it, she was able to determine her manner of speaking towards different individuals. She affirmed that:

“And the way you communicate with that specific individual should be fit. Like when I talk, talk with a friend, I can use informal approach, and when I talk with the instructors I must or I use formal approach.” (FGD 002)

Enhancing Language Proficiency and Communication Strategies. This theme is the last essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants’ in-depth interview and focus group discussion. Its codes are the following; linguistic knowledge and strategic competence in language use. The students stated that they believe language awareness to have influenced their linguistic knowledge, as well as their strategic competence in utilizing the English language in communication.

Consequently, Ms. Confident recognizes the importance of language awareness in her language learning. This is because, she believes that her language awareness serves as a mental repository of the language, from its words, to its functions. She affirmed that:

“Ah, I believe that students’ awareness of the English language has affects their effectiveness in communicating using English because their awareness serves as their mental repository of words and or phrases, or is called lexicon helping them in selecting appropriate words to be use in communicating with the words using the English language.” (IDI-01)

Also, Ms. Professional emphasized the role of language awareness as the understanding of the language system. Through her awareness, she was able to determine grammar rules, vocabulary, and word pronunciation. She affirmed that:

“Of course it encompasses your understanding of the rules, the grammar rules, your vocabulary, the way you pronounce the English words.” (IDI-02)

Additionally, Ms. Cutie emphasized that language awareness helps someone become an effective communicator. It is because, language awareness will serve as the mental guide of speakers in utilizing the language. She affirmed that:

“I believe that having language awareness really helps me to become an effective communicator of English, because it serves as my mental guide on what appropriate words to use, what proper pronunciation of words are...” (IDI-03)

On the other hand, Ms. Cutie recognizes the role of language awareness in language skills of students. It is because, due to her language awareness, she was able to repair her language usage, which enables her to express herself. She affirmed that:

“...og kana ganing makalimot ka sa English word nya pwede ra nako ma improvise, like explaining something but still the same ang meaning sa kato nga word nga akong nalimtan.” (IDI-03)

(as well as whenever I forgot the English word, I can just improvise, like explaining something but still the meaning is the same with the word that I forgot.)

Likewise, Mr. Shy also recognizes the role of language awareness in communication repair. He highlighted that due to it, he was able to identify alternative words to repair his communication process, which then enabled him to effectively share his thought. He affirmed that:

“I believe that having awareness of English language enables me to become a good communicator, since I will be able to know how to express myself more, and be able to choose alternative words if I forgot terms while talking or explaining.” (IDI-04)

Lastly, Ms. Cautious recognized that language awareness serves as a tool to improve effectiveness of communication. Through language awareness, she was able to express herself effectively, leading to her successful communication process. She affirmed that:

“I believe that students’ awareness of the English language affects their effectiveness in communicating using English to ah deliver or express their ideas well or comprehensibly...” (FGD-04)

The Insights of English Education Students with Regard to their Language Awareness

There are four essential themes which are created based on the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion on the second research question. They are; the importance of establishing engagement for effective language expression, the significance of foundational knowledge and communicative competence in learning a language, the interconnectedness of language learning and performances, and the value of employing variety of language materials and actual activities. The essential themes which emerged from the transcriptions of the participants’ responses for the research question number two consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

The Importance of Establishing Engagement for Effective Language Expression. This is one of the essential themes from responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the following codes: positive impact of language and effects on language use. The participants mentioned that there had been a positive impact of language awareness on their use and comprehension of the language.

Consequently, Ms. Cutie recognizes the importance of language awareness in her communication process. Through having language awareness, she was able to identify proper ways in utilizing the language to effectively impart her message. She affirmed that:

“Hmm, my reflection is that having language awareness really plays a part in my engagement in different contexts kay it serves as a

tool for me to really know how to express myself without misunderstandings or dili ma misleading akong istorya.” (IDI-03)

(My reflection is that having language awareness really plays a part in my engagement in different contexts kay it serves as a tool for me to really know how to express myself without misunderstandings or so that what I said will not be misleading.)

Table 4.2. *The Insights of English Education Students with Regard to Their Language Awareness*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Categories</i>	<i>Essential Theme</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Impact to engagement with others in different contexts	Ability to identify suitable choice of vocabulary in communicating in different contexts Sensitivity to semantic intention in utilizing the English language Enhances the overall language competence of individuals Utilizes language effectively in order to be understood by other people Fosters confidence in language use to effectively express oneself	Positive Impact of Language Effects on Language Use	The Importance of Establishing Engagement for Effective Language Expression	Linguistic Relativity Hypothesis
Purposes of language awareness in learning English language	Enables learners to identify the importance of learning English language Serves as a tool for understanding language rules and vocabulary when learning a language Serves as the background knowledge of the language being learned Serves as a tool in language competence which facilitates understanding of grammar rules and vocabulary Enables speakers to utilize the language based on their intention and motivation in communicating and based on the context they are in	Benefits of Learning a Language Language Knowledge and Its Usage	The Significance of Foundational knowledge and Communicative Competence in Learning a Language	Input Hypothesis Theory of Communicative Competence
Language awareness in building classroom engagement	Becoming receptive to new concept about the English language Facilitates language comprehension during classroom engagement Enables understanding to lessons during discussion Acquires knowledge to be taught in the field of language teaching Build confidence in language use inside the classroom Improves language proficiency in communication during class interactions	Language Learning Language Performances	The Interconnectedness of Language Learning and Performances	Usage-Based Theory
Improving language awareness	Engaging in different language activities Make use of different materials to gain more knowledge of English language Exposing oneself to the language to improve language knowledge and performance Practicing the use of English language through speaking and writing	Utilizing Different Learning Materials Providing Students with Exposure to Language	The Value of Employing Variety of Language Materials and Actual Activities	Experiential Learning Theory

Additionally, Mr. Shy stated that he recognizes its importance in his communication process as language awareness enables him to become aware of possible strategies that he should employ in order to deliver his message effectively. He affirmed that:

“I can share that it really is important to have a strong language awareness, as this is very beneficial especially in the field of our study which we communicate in different contexts that requires us to speak the language with different considerations in mind, like what is the correct things to say and what are the possible communication strategies we should employ.” (IDI-04)

Also, Ms. Nervous realized that having language awareness is important in order to adjust her communication practices to suit the situation she is in. Through this, she was able to effectively communicate her message or deliver her intentions effectively. She affirmed that:

“Language awareness made me realize and helps me to adjust my communicate in different situation and to consider what appropriate words I can use to a certain situation, that it can be through it can be applied through talking or writing.” (FGD-02)

Further, Ms. Cautious stated that due to her language awareness, she was able to properly choose appropriate words to be used in engaging with different individual in order for her to effectively impart her message. She affirmed that:

“For me, the impact of language awareness on ah engagement in different contexts or settings sor the impact of language awareness on engagement in different contexts or settings is that ah maha maingon nato ang gusto nato iingon and then we are able to kanang use certain words that is really fits what we’re going to express.” (FGD-04)

(For me, the impact of language awareness on engagement in different contexts or settings or the impact of language awareness on engagement in different contexts or settings is that we can say what we intend to say and then we are able to use certain words that really fits what we are going to express.)

On the other hand, Ms. Confident stated that due to her language awareness, she became more confident in expressing her idea. Also, she was able to utilize her knowledge of nuances which contributes to her overall language performance. She affirmed that:

“I would like to share to, I would like to share that language awareness significantly impact my engagement in various contexts or ah settings because language awareness fosters ah confidence in communication, enabling individuals to express themselves fluently and effectively in English. With a good grasp of language nuances, one can readily respond to questions and convey thoughts with clarity.” (IDI-01)

Furthermore, Ms. Professional recognize the important role of language awareness in facilitating her language performance. She stated that through it, she was able to identify proper words and pronunciation she should employ in her communication process. She affirmed that:

“...it equipped me with the ability to adapt my communication styles. Especially when I am presenting in front of the class, the way you communicate effectively to, to give emphasis to the tone, and of course the use of words, the vocabulary that really suits to the ah situations that you are in or the your ah, kung kinsa man ang mga audience or people na you’re presenting with, so, it could be formally and informally.” (IDI-02)

(...it equipped me with the ability to adapt my communication styles. Especially when I am presenting in front of the class, the way you communicate effectively, to give emphasis to the tone, and of course the use of words, the vocabulary that really suits to the situations that you are in or your audience or the people that you’re presenting to, so, it could be formally and informally.)

Then, Ms. Honest also recognizes the importance of language awareness as it enables speakers to utilize the language with competence. She affirmed that:

“As an English education student I think the importance of language awareness is it helps the user to have competence by performance of their own language.” (FGD-01)

Lastly, Ms. Cautious stated that through her language awareness, she was able to relate to others in the use of the English language. Thus, allowing her to covey her thoughts effectively as well. She affirmed that:

“And of course, we are able to relate to others, specifically when they are using English language that we could be able to understand their sides and we can share our thoughts and opinions as well.” (FGD-04)

The Significance of Foundational knowledge and Communicative Competence in Learning a Language. This is the second essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the following code; benefits of learning a language and language knowledge and its usage. The participants mentioned that having language awareness served as a factor that benefited them in their language learning as well as their use of the English language.

Consequently, Ms. Confident shared that her language awareness is an important factor in learning the English language. It is because, she sees it as a guide for her language learning process. She affirmed that:

“Ah, I perceive language awareness as an essential factor in English, in learning English language as it acts as a guide on how to easily and effectively learn English language.” (IDI-01)

Also, Ms. Cutie recognized language awareness as her motivation to learn the language since she was able to see language learning as a beneficial process in expanding her knowledge of the English language. She affirmed that:

“Hmm kuan kining, I perceive language awareness kuan kining, uhm mura syag factor nga ma motivate ka kay if naa kay language awareness kay kabalo ka sa importance sa pag learn sa language unya maexpand pajud nimo imong knowledge about the English language kay mas ma appreciate nimo if learn or your vocabulary will expand through learning man.” (IDI-03)

(I perceive language awareness as a factor that can motivate you, since if you have language awareness, you will know the importance of learning the language, and you will be able to expand your knowledge of the English language because you will appreciate it when

your vocabulary widens through learning.)

Additionally, Mr. Shy recognize language awareness as a factor that serves as the foundation of his knowledge of the target language. He affirmed that:

“Language awareness is an important factor in learning English language as this will serve as our prior knowledge and as well as our means of expanding our knowledge of the language.” (IDI-04)

Similarly, Ms. Expressive recognizes that her language awareness is a foundation for her to easily learn the English language. Through having it as her foundational knowledge, language learning becomes easier for her affirmed that:

“Language awareness is essential factor in learning English language because if the students have that as his or her foundation the student may easily learn the English language and use it to communicate effectively.”

Further, Ms. Cautious sees language awareness as a factor that serves as a foundational knowledge which contains her knowledge of the basic information of the language. She stated that her foundational knowledge is important in order for her to move to a higher form of knowledge about the language. She affirmed that:

“Language awareness as an important factor in learning English language because learning English language should start from basic to abstract or basic to high level. Because, you cannot go with the difficult or abstract one if you don’t know what is the basic one...” (FGD-04)

On the other hand, Ms. Professional recognizes that language awareness enables her to know the functions of the language as well as its usage. Through her understanding of the language, she was able to perform the language with competence and improve her overall language comprehension. She affirmed that:

“...you’re not just learning the words, what is the English term, but you are also learning to understand how it works, understanding the grammar, we can use the words, the vocabulary, their meanings and of course, the pronunciation as well. So, by having that awareness, by having these elements, of course learners, or users can really use the English language effectively, and they can communicate clearly, and of course, you can comprehend the meanings that are used in different context.” (IDI-02)

Then, Ms. Unready recognizes that her language awareness is a factor that enables her to recognize the rules of language and how it is used. She affirmed that:

“I perceive language awareness as an important factor in learning English language in a way that if we have language awareness we can learn the language rules and when uncovering words that is somehow difficult.” (IDI-05)

Lastly, Ms. Nervous recognizes the important role of language awareness in fostering her language knowledge. Through this, she is able to see the deeper sense of language. She affirmed that:

“Language awareness plays a crucial for learning English because it will help me understand deeper sense of language such as in the grammar, in rules and the like.” (FGD-02)

The Interconnectedness of Language Learning and Performances. This is another essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the following code; language learning and language performance. The participants highlighted that having language awareness allowed them to be more engaging in a classroom setting which utilizes the English language as a means for communication.

Consequently, Ms. Confident stated that her language awareness is important as an English education student, since it helps her in her language learning. Through her language awareness, she becomes more open to acquiring information about the language, as well as improve her language skills. She affirmed that:

“As an English education student, possessing language awareness is significant in my classroom engagement because it facilitates my learning process. When I am aware of language nuances, I become more receptive to new concepts and more open to addressing areas where I may be lacking.” (IDI-01)

Also, Ms. Nervous recognizes the role of language awareness in becoming an effective communicator. Also, this enables her to be confident in her capability to use and comprehend the English language. She affirmed that:

“So as an English major student, English education student, possessing language awareness is really important to become effective and not only to become effective, but also confident. So having that awareness really enables you to be confident in analyzing, and communicating, and also to be proficient educator in the field.” (FGD-02)

Similarly, Ms. Expressive recognizes that language awareness serves as her role in equipping herself with the knowledge she needs in her teaching career. She stated that her language awareness will enable her to become a teacher who is aware of the appropriate language she should utilize in the classroom. She affirmed that:

“As an English Education student, since I am a future language teacher, it is important to possess Language awareness in order for me to become an effective teacher wherein I can teach effectively to my students utilizing the English language and also a teacher who knows what words appropriate to use based on students’ level of learning.” (FGD-03)

Likewise, Ms. Patient recognizes the importance of language awareness. She stated that possessing language awareness will enable her to become an effective and efficient educator. She affirmed that:

“As an English education student, it is significant to possess language awareness in order for me to become an efficient and effective teacher in the future.” (FGD-05)

On the other hand, Ms. Cutie recognizes language awareness as a tool to be aware of the use of the language. Thus, enabling her to be effective in her classroom engagement. She affirmed that:

“Hmm it is very significant te kay as an English educator student, education student, we need to know ah hmm we need, kana ganing makabalo ta unsaon pag gamit sa English language like, we should be able to communicate using the English language effectively inside the classroom, dili lang kay inig mag oral, but also in engaging in class discussions. Especially po nga gina require jud ta mag English sa uban nato instructors.” (IDI-03)

(It is very significant because as an English student, we need to be able to know how to use the English language like, we should be able to communicate using the English language effectively inside the classroom, not just during oral recitation, but also in engaging in class discussions. Especially that we are being required to speak in English by our instructors.)

Additionally, Mr. Shy recognized the importance of language awareness as it enables him to utilize the English language more effectively. Through utilizing the language, he was able to participate in classroom activities. He affirmed that:

“It is very significant, since as an English education student, I really need to be able to use English language in my classroom engagement, such as in oral recitation or simply in participating in class, and having language awareness will enable me to effectively do so.” (IDI-04)

Lastly, Ms. Nervous stated that language awareness is important in order to have an understanding of the language, thus contributing to her understanding during discussions. Also, she stated that it also enables her to participate in class discussion effectively. She affirmed that:

“So, having language awareness is really important as an English education student, because it helps me to understand the lessons better, communicate clearly, and participate effectively in class discussions.” (FGD-02)

The Value of Employing Variety of Language Materials and Actual Activities. This is the last essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the following code; utilizing different learning materials and providing students with exposure to language. The students mentioned that in order to improve one’s language awareness, they should utilize different materials to expand their knowledge of the language, as well as create opportunity for language exposure in order to improve their language performance.

Consequently, Ms. Confident stated that language awareness may improve through utilization of different materials. Through employing these materials, students will be engaged with different usage of the language which improves their overall language awareness. She affirmed that:

“So, to improve their language awareness, I recommend students to engage more actively in the language learning activities and discussions, for them to have deeper understanding and also, the mastery of the language.” (IDI-01)

Also, Ms. Cutie stated that students should first know the importance of learning the language. After that, they may utilize different materials to engage themselves to the target language which then contributes to the development of their language awareness. She affirmed that:

“...they should learn first the importance of the language, its use, and then after that, if they are finally aware of the importance, they should engage themselves in, like, reading English books or to watch movies with English language...” (IDI-03)

Furthermore, Mr. Shy recognizes the importance of exposure to different materials in improving the knowledge of the learner about the language, since this will enable them to develop their language awareness. He affirmed that:

“I recommend to other students that they should engage themselves in situation that they will become more exposed to the English language like watching movies, listening to music, and, there are many more.” (IDI-04)

Similarly, Ms. Honest suggests to engage in literary pieces or even movies in order to be acquainted with more information about the language. Through this, students will be able to improve their language awareness. She affirmed that:

“I think my suggestion is to have a reading, reading different books literature as well as different writing style, to enhance the vocabulary, also listen or watch foreign movies.” (FGD-01)

Likewise, Ms. Expressive also suggested to utilize literary pieces to engage with the target language. This would widen the vocabulary of the students, contributing to their overall language awareness. She affirmed that:

“I would recommend to them to read more books or literatures to widen their vocabulary. And also, they may also utilize applications that would help them learn or improve their language awareness...” (FGD-03)

Then, Ms. Cautious also suggested to utilize literature in order to be acquainted with different vocabulary. Through this, they will be able to improve their language awareness as it will provide them with opportunity to engage with the target language. She affirmed that:

“...they should engage their selves in literatures, reading stories, reading more books, reading more novel stories, so they could be able to encounter different words and then widen their vocabulary and if they don’t know the word then they may or they can search it so that their knowledge will expand.” (FGD-04)

On the other hand, Ms. Professional emphasized the importance of exposing the learner to the target language. Through this exposure, the learner will be able to practice the use of language, which will develop their language awareness. She affirmed that:

“...to really engage in a conversation wherein the English language is, or there will be exposure to the language, a great help for you to really learn by actually using the language.” (IDI-02)

Additionally, Ms. Nervous emphasized the importance of language practice to be help improve language skills. Through this exposure, the learner will be able to enhance their capabilities in communication. She affirmed that:

“And also, students can practice speaking and writing in English regularly to enhance their language skills and to build confidence. And we can also, or student can also, listen to English speakers and try to copy or mimic their pronunciation and intonation which enhances their abilities in communication.” (FGD-02)

Lastly, Ms. Patient also stated the importance of practicing the language in order to develop the language awareness of students. This is because, she believed that practicing will enable them to become good users of the target language. She affirmed that:

“...practice in real-life settings in order for them to become good users of the English language.” (FGD-05)

Data Integration of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Exploring the Language Awareness of English Education Students. The study shows that the quantitative and qualitative phase of the study converged when merged its findings and results. Specifically, Table 2 of Affective Domain item 4 and 5, respectively, find learning the English language easier if I can relate it to real life situation and find English language useful and important for communication inside and outside the school with the mean of 4.23 and 4.33 with both high descriptive equivalents, and the qualitative result on Table 4.1 on the lived experiences of English education students with regard to their language awareness highlights the code application in real-world context under the theme of gaining motivation for language learning and teaching.

Table 5. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Aspect Or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature Of Data Integration	Axiological Implications
Language Awareness	Table 2 of Affective Domain item 4, finding learning the English language easier if I can relate it to real life situation, had an equivalent description of high with M=4.23.	Table 4.1 on application in real-world context under the codes Preparation towards Teaching Profession and Application in Real-world Context and highlighting the theme Gaining Motivation for Language Learning and Teaching.	Merging-converging	Students find language learning easier if they can apply their learning to real-world situations and as they prepare themselves towards the teaching profession.
	Table 2 of Affective Domain item 5, finding English language useful and important for communication inside and outside the school, had an equivalent description of very high with M=4.33.			
Language Awareness	Table 2 of Social Domain item 1, can determine what form of language to use in different contexts or settings, had an equivalent description of high with M=3.93.	Table 4.1 on the codes Using Word Choice in Different Context and Formality of Speaking and highlighting the theme Having Different Means of Identifying Proper Approach in Communication.	Merging-converging	Students become more aware of their word choice when having communication with different individuals and this shows how important is to have language awareness in fostering effective communication.
	Table 2 of Social Domain item 2, can communicate well with people with different cultures and behaviors, had an equivalent description of high with M=3.80.			
	Table 2 of Cognitive Domain item 1, considering proper words to use in a			

situation or conversation, had an equivalent description of high with M=4.21.

Table 2 of Power Domain item 2, understanding what is being said to me even in a figurative sense, had an equivalent description of high with M=3.75.

Table 2 of Power Domain item 3, can identify hidden meanings within texts I read or hear, had an equivalent description of high with M=3.76.

Table 2 of Cognitive Domain item 5, can recognize different parts of speech in English, had an equivalent description of high with M=3.87.

Table 2 of Performance Domain item 1, can communicate well with others using the English language, had an equivalent description of high with M=3.88.

Table 2 of Performance Domain item 2, can speak what I intend to say using the English language, had an equivalent description of high with M=3.83.

Table 4.1 on the codes Skills Developed in English Language and Making Interpretation of Text Meaning which are under the theme Having the Ability to Uncover Underlying Meanings and Messages in Texts.

Table 4.1 on the codes Benefits of Learning a Language and Language Knowledge and Its Usage which are under the theme The Significance of Foundational Knowledge and Communicative Competence in Learning a Language.

Table 4.1 on the codes Positive Impact of Language and Effects on Language Use which are under the theme The Importance of Establishing Engagement for Effective Language Expression.

Merging-converging

Merging-converging

Merging-converging

This highlighted the importance of language awareness of students in becoming aware of the hidden or figurative meaning within a certain sentence or text.

This showed the importance of language awareness in building up knowledge of basic rules as functions of English language.

This emphasized how language awareness of students enables them to utilize language effectively in conveying their thoughts or messages.

Also, another result has shown from both quantitative and qualitative phase revealed parallel findings. For the quantitative phase on Table 2 of Social Domain item 1 and 2 respectively can determine what form of language to use in different contexts or settings and can communicate well with people with different cultures and behaviors with the mean of 3.93 and 3.80 with both high descriptive equivalents, and the qualitative result on Table 4.1 on the lived experiences of English education students with regard to their language awareness highlights the code using word choice in different context and formality of speaking under the theme of having different means of identifying proper approach in communication.

Additionally, the same converging findings revealed on quantitative result on Table 4.1 on the level of language awareness of English Education students in term of their power domain item 2 and 3 respectively understand what is being said to me even in a figurative sense and can identify hidden meanings within texts I read or hear with the mean of 3.75 and 3.76 with both high descriptive equivalents, and the qualitative result on Table 4.1 on the lived experiences of English education students with regard to their language awareness highlights the code making interpretation of text meaning under the theme of having the ability to uncover underlying meanings and messages in texts.

Furthermore, another salient result from both quantitative and qualitative phase revealed parallel findings. For the quantitative phase on Table 4.1 on the level of language awareness of English Education students in terms of their cognitive domain item 5 can recognize different parts of speech in English with the mean of 3.87 with high descriptive equivalent, and the qualitative result on Table 4.1 on the lived experiences of English education students with regard to their language awareness highlights the code benefits of learning a language and language knowledge and its usage under the theme the significance of foundational knowledge and communicative competence in learning a language.

Lastly, the same converging findings revealed on quantitative result on Table 4.1 on the level of language awareness of English Education students in terms of their performance domain item 1 and 2 respectively can communicate well with others using the English language and can speak what I intend to say using the English language with the mean of 3.88 and 3.83 with both high descriptive equivalents, and the qualitative result on Table 4.1 on the lived experiences of English education students with regard to their language awareness highlights the code positive impact of language and effects on language use under the theme of the importance of establishing engagement for effective language expression.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the level of language awareness of English education students is high in terms of their five domains, namely, affective domain, social domain, power domain, cognitive domain, and performance domain. Hence, this indicates that the students show positive level of awareness in the indicators of language awareness.

Second, the thematic analysis of the qualitative data was done based from the responses gained through the conduct of in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). The results gave more information about the lived experiences of English education students with regard to their language awareness. The following essential themes emerged: gaining motivation for language learning and teaching, having the ability to uncover underlying meanings and messages in texts, utilizing English as a tool for effective communication, having different means of identifying proper approach in communication, and enhancing language proficiency and communication strategies.

Third, from the participants responses, other essential themes are identified which show their insights with regard to their language awareness which are: the importance of establishing engagement for effective language expression, the significance of foundational knowledge and communicative competence in learning a language, the interconnectedness of language learning and performances, and the value of employing variety of language materials and actual activities.

Lastly, to better understand the language awareness of English education students, the responses were analyzed thematically to confirm the quantitative results of the study. Both the findings from the two phases are integrated based on the nature plan. The level of language awareness of English education students based on the quantitative results show that it converged to the data gained from the qualitative phase. Both of the quantitative and qualitative results confirms that having language awareness enables students to gain sensitivity to language learning and use in different contexts which contributes to the overall language performance of the students.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Given that the results indicate that the power domain of language awareness has the lowest mean among the five indicators, which negatively impacts students' ability to recognize hidden meanings in texts and understand figurative language, it is advisable for students to immerse themselves in literature that challenges their understanding of language. They should explore various literary works and reflect on the underlying meanings or the author's intentions behind each piece. Additionally, teachers could implement activities designed to help students practice using language figuratively and improve their skills in identifying and interpreting figurative expressions. Parents are also encouraged to foster an appreciation for figurative language by motivating their children to explore the depths of language learning. Furthermore, the Department of Education should introduce programs aimed at enhancing students' language awareness, particularly in their comprehension of figurative language. Engaging students in interactive games may also prove beneficial in developing their power domain, as such activities can make learning enjoyable and reinforce their understanding of figurative language.

Additionally, based from the qualitative phase results on the lived experiences of English education students with regard to their language awareness, they may utilize different materials that will expose them to the language, and even expose themselves to an environment which utilizes the target language. By constant exposure to the language, their language awareness will develop in terms of language use in diverse context, appropriateness of their word choice, and even proper utilization of language, which will then help them in their teaching career when facing diverse learners. Hence, from their experiences in using the language, they should be aware of the role that language awareness plays in order for them to recognize the importance in continually improving it.

Consequently, those shared insight of English education students with regard to their language awareness may help them develop their language awareness. Also, having new perspectives to the role that language awareness plays in both their language learning and language use may enable them to improve their use of the target language. Teachers may also impart to the students a different perspective of language awareness in their language teaching, as well as utilize language awareness activities in their learning process.

Moreover, the researcher recommends that in teaching literature to students, teachers may incorporate differentiated tasks focusing on making the students see the functions of the language in conveying the overall message of literary pieces. Also, students should create opportunities for themselves to be able to utilize the English language even outside the classrooms or school contexts. Lastly, students should reflect on how their language awareness impacts their overall journey in the English education field.

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